

**THE MYSTICAL AND THE MUNDANE: RAMCHANDRA GANDHI'S
LIVED ADVAITA AND THE NON-DUAL REALISATION OF THE SELF**

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Abstract

The paper examines Ramchandra Gandhi's philosophical interpretation of *Advaitic* self-realisation as developed in his seminal work *I Am Thou*. He developed his claims that, without the union of the self and other, there can be no relationships, yet challenges the conventional separation between the mystical and the profane. He situates the realisation of the oneness of the self and the other in the mystical realm, which needs to be actualised in everyday life. For him, self-realisation is not an isolated mystical attainment, separated from the world, but ought to reflect in our ordinary relationship with the world. The paper explores his *Advaitic* interpretation of self as a manifestation of a shared non-dual essence that dissolves binaries of the self and the other, sacred and profane. The paper brings out his articulation of how the mystical is actualised through ethical engagement in our relational awareness and compassionate living towards the other. The paper also examines how he extends his *Advaitic* insights into the crisis of contemporary social and interpersonal life, shaped by a dualistic outlook. In a world increasingly shaped by the conflicting tendencies of collectivism, individualism, and ideological polarisation, the paper brings forth his distinct *Advaita* calls for a mode of living that is reflective, inclusive, and attuned to the non-dual interconnectedness of all existence.

Keywords: Self, Other, Non-duality, Mystical, Profane, and Mundane.

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Introduction

Advaita Vedānta, an Indian school of thought, affirms the oneness of the self (*Ātman*) and ultimate reality (*Brahman*), thereby radically repudiating the dualistic understanding of the self and the other. However, the interpretation of classical *Advaita* has not been exhausted, in privileging mystical transcendence over the renunciation of worldly life. Many contemporary thinkers of *Advaita* have reinterpreted it as a spiritual union that must reflect lived human experience. Ramchandra Gandhi, among the contemporary interpreters of Advaita Vedānta, offers a lived *Advaita*. He initiated not merely the truth of *Advaita*, but in the world. His interpretation of lived *Advaita* is reflected in his philosophical writings, which firmly uphold the *Advaitic* understanding of the self as not a withdrawal from the world, but a perception of the world as already sacred, seeking to reconcile mystical insight with the ethical, relational, and everyday dimensions of life.

The paper examines his distinctive contribution to living *Advaita*, embodying the non-dual vision amid the ordinary human everyday life. In his interpretation, the mystical and the mundane are not opposed, but are intimately intertwined in the realisation of the self. Given the philosophical depth and contemporary relevance of his rethinking of *Advaita*, this

paper explores his interpretation of the inherent potential of the practicality of lived *Advaita* by critically engaging with his account of the *Advaitic* relation between the self and the other, particularly as expressed in his seminal work *I Am Thou*. In doing so, it hopes to contribute to a discourse that affirms the sacredness of everyday life in an age marked by fragmentation, alienation, and spiritual disenchantment.

Ramchandra Gandhi (2011) offers a distinctive interpretation of the self and the other, grounding his approach in the assertion that *Advaita*, non-duality, represents not merely a philosophical doctrine but the ultimate truth of India and of all reality. He contends that *Advaita* constitutes a radical repudiation of otherness, affirming that *Ātman* (Self) is the ultimate and sole reality (Gandhi, 2011). The *Advaitic* view of the self-demands a departure from the conventional or empirical framework of identity, as it transcends the psychological, social, and personal determinants of individuality. He distinguishes the conviction of self-identity from any cognitive assertion or experimental awareness of the self. Instead, it is an existential conviction, a fundamental certainty about one's being. As he articulates, "one could say that it is the conviction of *Advaita*, of not-being-two-or-more, to put it negatively, and to being-oneself, to put it positively, which is both a

conviction of being-one, and of being oneself.” (Gandhi, 2019, pp. 49-50). Rooted in the metaphysics of Advaita Vedānta, this view maintains that the apparent multiplicity of selves and the external world arises from *Avidyā*, ignorance of the underlying unity of being. Central to *Advaita* philosophy is the insight that the differentiation between the self and the other is illusory; more radically, it upholds that the self (*Ātman*) is non-different from the ultimate reality, *Brahman*. Śāṅkarācārya’s commentary on the *Īśā Upaniṣad* underscores this by asserting that, in the *Vedic* text, the self is none other than the indwelling essence of all beings: “ ‘As the indwelling Self (of all), I am all this’; all this that is unreal, whether moving or not moving, is to be covered by one’s own self” (Śāṅkarācārya, 2023, p. 5). Here, the self is not a psychological construct or egoic entity but the ground of being, prior to conceptual distinctions and beyond phenomenal identification. It is regarded as the highest truth, transcending all imagination, discrimination and the diversified outlook of the phenomenal world, liberated from anger, fear and attachment of all forms and kinds (Śāṅkarācārya, 2023). In this light, *Advaitic* self-realisation is not at metaphysical abstraction, but a transformative reorientation of vision, a shift in consciousness that discloses the

sacredness immanent in all beings and modes of existence.

In Advaita Vedānta, the notion of *Ātman* as the ultimate reality is a foundational metaphysical principle. This conception is systematically articulated by early *Advaita* thinkers such as Gaudapāda, Śāṅkara, and Ramana Maharṣi. As C.D. Sharma notes in *A Critical Survey of Indian Philosophy*, Gaudapāda, regarded as the first systematic expounder of *Advaita*, draws heavily from the *Upaniṣads* – particularly the *Māṅdūkya*, *Bṛhadāraṇyaka*, and *Chāṅdogya* – to establish the self (*Ātman*) as the sole reality. (Sharma, 2025). Sharma observes that the *Brahmasūtra* and the *Bhagavad Gītā* may also inform Gaudapāda’s metaphysics, as he posits that “reality is the pure self which is pure consciousness and which is at the background of everything.” (Sharma, 2025, p. 246.) Gaudapāda affirms the non-dual nature of the Absolute (*Ātman*) through the well-known analogy of superimposition of the rope and the snake: “The imagination of the *Ātman* as different things and the imagination of different things themselves, which in fact do not exist, depend on the Non-duality Absolute or the Pure *Ātman*, just as the imagination of a snake, in the case of a rope-snake, depends upon the rope. The Absolute alone, therefore, is blissful.” (Gaudapāda, *Māṅdūkya Kārikā*, as cited in Sharma, 2025, p. 243). In this framework, the empirical

world is viewed as illusory (*Māyā*), with all multiplicity superimposed upon the one undivided reality of the self. Śaṅkara, the disciple of Gaudapāda, further elaborates and deepens this non-dualist vision. He unequivocally identifies *Ātman* with *Brahman*, asserting that the self is pure consciousness, self-luminous, and transcends the dualities inherent in empirical cognition: “Everything else is relative and therefore ultimately unreal. The self alone is not relative. It is therefore, self-proved.” (Śaṅkara, *Kena-Vākya-Bhāṣya*, as cited in Sharma, 2025, P. 283).

A new dimension of Advaita Vedānta emerges from the interpretation articulated by Ramana Maharṣi. Ranchandra Gandhi notes that Ramana Maharṣi revitalised Advaita by actualising it as a lived reality: “This would be in 1984 merely a philosophical standpoint has not until only about three decades ago lived among us in India Śrī Ramana Maharṣi who taught without fear of contradiction and lived impregnable to doubt and cynicism the truth of *Ātman-Brahman*...” “This is most evident in Ramana’s use of the term ‘I-I’ (*aham-aham, nāṇ-nāṇ*) as the best locution to signify the immediate flash of liberating consciousness” (Forsthoefel, 2003, p. 110). He is hailed as a “mystic of the first order” (Bharati, 1976, p. 29). He propounded a lived and experiential path of self-enquiry that communicates the immediacy of non-dual

awareness. He states, “the enquiry in the form of ‘who am I?’, is the principle means for self-realisation (Ramana, 2024, p 5). At the core of his teaching lies the question ‘who am I?’, which calls for a sustained inquiry into the sources of thought, the rejection of mental identifications, and ultimately the transcendence of the mind itself. “This ‘I’ is only the ego, or the ‘I’ thought. After the rising up of this ‘I’ thought, all other thoughts arises. The ‘I’ thought is therefore the root thought. If the root is pulled out, all the rest is at the same time uprooted” (Osborne, 2014, p. 114). This introspective examination of consciousness, according to Ramana Maharṣi, issues in the direct experience of the self. Such realisation “culminate in the resolution of all conditions into the blissful non-dual awareness, one’s original state (*sahaja sthiti*)” (Forsthoefel, 2003, p. 128). Through self-enquiry, guided by the penetrating question “who am I?”, Ramana Maharṣi initiates the inward quest culminating in self-realisation. In this way, he advances a program of religious knowing, “a knowing beyond knowledge” (Forsthoefel, 2001. P. 34). Makarand Paranjpe, in his reflection on Ramana Maharṣi’s life and teachings, considers “*Advaita Vedānta* is not simply an abstract system of philosophy involving idle speculation, but a practical philosophy of life, involving a form of applied psychology that can effectively guide a person’s self-

realisation” (Paranjpe, 2013, p 364). The early *Advaita* thinkers Gaudapāda, Śaṅkara, and Ramana Maharṣi affirm that *Ātman*, pure, non-dual consciousness, is not merely a metaphysical postulate but the ultimate reality, as claimed, rooted in the *Upanisadic* vision and central to Advaita Vedānta.

Raised in a Hindu tradition, Ramchandra Gandhi’s interpretation of Advaita Vedānta is deeply rooted in the metaphysical vision articulated by the early thinkers of the tradition, particularly Gaudapāda, Śaṅkara and Ramana Maharṣi. His bold affirmation of *Advaita* as a universal truth in his seminal work *I Am Thou* may be seen as a contemporary continuation and creative reactualisation of the non-dualist insight into the self, while also reflecting his sustained and critical engagement with Western philosophical thought. His commitment to *Advaita* was grounded in religious tradition, yet enriched by his conversance with modern Western philosophy, enabling him to reinterpret *Advaitic* insights in a modern light. Shail Mayaram (2013) noted that Ramchandra Gandhi advocates an alternative classificatory framework for the ‘world religions’ that does not differentiate between Eastern and Western religions. A typology that accommodates differences, but also the idea that there can be shared and overlapping visions of the divine between different religious traditions, as well as

divergent cosmologies within what is thought of as a single religious tradition. This perspective is also echoed in Ramachandra Guha’s account, where Ramchandra Gandhi supported Gandhi’s call for each faith to deepen its own truths while respecting others, seeing religion as a ground for fellowship where unity arises through mutual respect rather than conversion, a stance that reflects his vision of unity in religion (Guha, 2008).

Through his approach to the unity of religion, he developed a distinctive understanding of Advaita in his book *I Am Thou*, claiming India as the only civilisational principle par excellence for restoring the complexity and variety of human spiritual and secular life (Gandhi, 2011). He defines *Advaita* in a non-exclusivist way by expanding the Indian religious, philosophical and spiritual tradition of *Advaita* towards all religions: “Advaitins appear everywhere, but India is the only sustained *sruti*-sanctified tradition of non-duality that we know of” (Gandhi, 2011, p. 17). Paranjape (2013) also acknowledges that Ramchandra Gandhi articulates and philosophises *Advaita* as a truth that sustains the world in a profoundly cross-cultural and transdisciplinary manner, as he did in his book *I Am Thou*.

A distinctive feature of Ramchandra Gandhi’s interpretation of *Advaita* lies in his engagement with the *Upanishads* and other

Indian religious texts as sources of insight, while notably refraining from directly quoting them. Sundar Sarukkai argues that Ramchandra Gandhi's *I Am Thou* is less a systematic engagement with *Advaita's* metaphysical principles and more an interpretative attempt to help us reclaim the experience of ultimate truth (Sarukkai, 2013). Along similar lines, V. Sanil notes that "Ramu never quotes any *ślokas* or sources that sanctioned his invocation of *Advaita*" (Sanil, 2013, p. 9), leading some to question whether he had even engaged with classical texts. However, this absence highlights Ramchandra Gandhi's deeper concern, not with textual fidelity, but with actualising *Advaita* as a lived, relational truth to be engaged and exercised in the world, a vision that transcends social and cultural constructs and remains universally accessible to all, irrespective of cultural or societal boundaries.

This paper is structured in three sections to critically examine Ramchandra Gandhi's vision of *Advaita*, particularly his emphasis on the oneness of reality and the need for its actualisation in everyday life. The first section investigates his conceptual articulation of the self and the other within the *Advaitic* framework, emphasising his view that self-realisation is rooted in the essence of *Brahman*. To develop this argument, the section engages with Ramchandra Gandhi's articulation of the

three central *Advaitic* concepts – *Ātman*, *Brahman*, and *Māyā* in his work *I Am Thou*, which together form the metaphysical foundation of Advaita Vedānta and reveal the inherent non-duality between the self and the other. The second section extends this inquiry by examining Ramchandra Gandhi's conception of 'telos' within the *Advaitic* idea of the self, arguing that the union of self and other must not remain a theoretical ideal but should be consciously enacted within the ordinary, everyday world. The third section examines the significance of his philosophical contribution and its contemporary relevance. In doing so, the paper ultimately seeks to assess the contemporary relevance of Ramchandra Gandhi's philosophy in an era increasingly shaped by the tensions between individualism and collectivism.

This paper engages with philosophical issues through the lens of Ramchandra Gandhi, adopting a primarily critical, textual, and hermeneutical method. These methods are employed to unpack the deeper interpretative and experimental dimensions of his thoughts, particularly his philosophy of the self and the other, emphasising their intrinsic unity and interrelatedness within the *Advaitic* framework of non-duality.

The *Advaitic* Notion of the Self and the Other

***Brahman* as the Ground of Non-Dual Selfhood**

Ramchandra Gandhi's engagement with *Advaitic* philosophy offers a profound interpretation of the self and the other through the interrelated concepts of *Ātman*, *Brahman*, and *Māyā*, elucidating the *Advaitic* understanding of the self. His exposition clarifies the *Advaitic* understanding of the self as fundamentally non-dual. According to *Advaitic* thought, the *Ātman* (self) is none other than the ultimate reality (*Brahman*), conceived as *Ātman-Brahman*. *Ātman-Brahman* is one without a second (*Advitīya*), an undivided reality that "can eternally remain unaltered in its self-image of *Advitīya* oneness" (Gandhi, 2011, p. 38). The concept of *Ātman-Brahman* involves a radical renunciation of ignorance and the continuous dissolution of false identification with the not-self, an act of self-differentiation that pervades all aspects of reality, including living and non-living beings (Gandhi, 2011). All things, from this perspective, exist in the light of *Ātman-Brahman*. Any apparent independent reality, apart from *Ātman-Brahman*, is ultimately illusory.

The core truth inherent in *Advaitic* principles can raise several questions: How is the unification of the self and the other possible? Does the world self stand meaningful if no independent others exist? Suppose there is no polarity between the

self and the other. Can there be communication between the self and the other? This section primarily examines Ramchandra Gandhi's articulation of *Ātman*, *Brahman*, and *Māyā* concepts, drawing mainly from his work *I Am Thou*, to engage with the philosophical issue arising from the unity of the self and the other.

Rather than viewing *Māyā* merely as a deceptive force that veils the truth, Ramchandra Gandhi offers a profound reinterpretation of the interrelatedness of *Ātman*, *Brahman*, and *Māyā* within the *Advaitic* tradition by emphasising the indispensable role of *Māyā* in the process of self-realisation. He conceptualises it as a necessary metaphysical principle that enables the very experience of duality and the subsequent realisation of non-duality. For Ramchandra Gandhi, *Māyā* explains the mysterious principle of the originator of the apparent manifestation of otherness, which serves as a means for *Ātman's* self-realisation from the ignorance of its true nature (Gandhi, 2011). In his reading, *Māyā* is not simply an illusion to be overcome but a revelatory medium through which the *Ātman* recognises its identity with *Brahman*. The reflection of *Brahman* in the form of appearance (*Mayā*) has no less power than *Brahman* itself: "the real can have no power greater than its power of appearance as unreality, and the power of resolving the

most recalcitrant appearance of unreality into itself" (Gandhi, 2011, p. 105).

It raises a fundamental philosophical question: If the apparent otherness is none other than *Brahman*, what is the need for the existence of an apparent otherness at all? Suppose the apparent otherness is none other than *Brahman*. Does that imply that the apparent otherness embodies a substantial reality as *Brahman*? Ramchandra Gandhi responds by suggesting that the apparent otherness is not a negation of *Brahman*, but an expression of its plenitude and creativity. By veiling the truth of oneness, *Māyā* makes possible the journey of the self from ignorance to knowledge, from separation to unity. As he writes, "other than *Ātman-Brahman*, there is only *Mayā*, illusion's self-annulling order of that which is neither real in the sense of necessary indubitable existence, the logical mark of identity only of *Ātman-Brahman*, nor unreal in the sense of blatant self-contradiction" (Gandhi, 2011, P. 110). Through this lens, the triadic relationship between *Ātman*, *Brahman*, and *Māyā* emerges not as a metaphysical problem to be resolved, but as a dynamic process integral to the unfolding of self-realisation.

He further explores the nature of *Brahman* as both resting and manifesting – a mysterious dual potential that reveals its intrinsic fullness. He suggests that the attainment of ultimate realisation lies in

one's thought that he is the ultimate reality and the ability to see oneness in the manyness of apparent reality. As the ground of all being, *Brahman* is understood as the perfect autonomous reality, which does not depend on the existence of others to affirm itself. It is echoed in the notion that "*Nirākāra Ātman-Brahman* in its deep autonomy rests in the thought 'I am that I am'" (Gandhi, 2011, p. 115), capturing the self-sufficiency of *Brahman* as the resting, unchanging source. At the same time, *Ātman-Brahman* must also be conceived as mysterious *Bhedābheda*, *Ātman-Brahman* playing in and as the thought: "I am *Rāsalīlā*, *Rāmarājya*, alchemical identity of parts with parts and with the whole" (Gandhi, 2011, p. 115). In his view, the dual nature of Brahman, as manifest in the Advaitic doctrine, enables the self to realise that *Ātman* is no different from *Brahman* and to understand that the myriad existences of beings and entities are not illusions to be dismissed but divine manifestations of *Brahman* itself. He writes, "All fruitfulness of alternation and adventure is situated within the self, within you and me who are one" (Gandhi, 2011, p. 139).

Building on this understanding, Ramchandra Gandhi argues that the most profound mystery we can conceive lies in the paradoxical act by which *Brahman* permits itself to be scattered – enveloped in

Avidyā and the fragmentation of pure consciousness into finite centres of selfhood. As he states, “*Ātman-Brahman* should permit such a scattering of itself, an enveloping of itself in the *Avidyā* of separate self-consciousness and the greatest sacrifice that we can imagine, the self-sacrifice of a possible eternal self- image of perfection in the form of an infinity of apparently finite centres of self-consciousness, each permitted the delusion of finite self-sufficiency, but all drawn by the very dialectic of self-consciousness, by the power of *Ātmavicāra*, into the one and only one real self-sufficiency which is the *Ātmabodha* of *Ātman-Brahman*” (Gandhi, 2011, pp. 38-39). In continuity with his emphasis on *Māyā* as the medium of concealment and revelation, he views this dispersion as essential to the metaphysical unfolding of self-realisation. From his perspective, and in line with *Advaitic* thought, the existence of others as distinct entities does not contradict non-duality but rather signifies *Brahman’s* possibility, potential and permission. Through *Māyā*, *Brahman’s* act of differentiation gives rise to apparent multiplicity while simultaneously holding the power to unify all as one.

***Māyā* as the Sacred Veil of the other:
A Medium for Self-Realisation**

The mystical interplay, as Ramchandra Gandhi suggests, leads us to a deeper metaphysical tension. As he contends

that *Brahman’s* mysterious function transcends ordinary human cognition, occupying a space that verges on the mystical realm, if all reality is ultimately non-dual, why does the world appear fragmented into distinct, finite selves and realities? The mystic nature of *Brahman*, Ramchandra Gandhi observes, raises profound questions that invite philosophical contemplation: why is there a persistent tendency for the infinite to manifest as the finite, for the undivided to appear divided, and for the one to take on the guise of many? In alignment with *Ramchandra Gandhi*, within the *Advaitic* framework, such multiplicity is not a contradiction of unity but *Brahman’s* own shadow. He states, “the shadow of God cannot be without its daunting substantiality” (Gandhi, 2011, p. 69). *Brahman*, in its mysterious permissiveness, allows its own shadow to manifest as the appearance of otherness, though always at the risk of being mistaken for independent existence. This shadow, identified as *Māyā*, conceals the ultimate truth while simultaneously enabling its gradual disclosure (Gandhi, 2011). For him, *Māyā* possesses the paradoxical power to project the oneness of reality into finite forms, each bearing the illusion of autonomy, yet none truly separate from the one. While the apparent distinctness of realities may perpetuate the illusion of separateness, it also constitutes the

necessary condition for the unfolding of self-realisation – “not-self is necessarily a feature of *Ātman-Brahman's* self-knowledge by way of negation or rejection” (Gandhi, 2011, p. 111). The play of *Māyā* may either prolong or obscure the recognition of the non-dual truth; nevertheless, it remains imperative to unfold the *Ātman-Brahman* relationship through a process of differentiation and return, ultimately enabling the realisation of their essential unity.

For Ramchandra Gandhi, the appearance of multiplicity is not a denial of reality but a distinctive mode through which reality affirms its dynamic self-identity. He interprets the *Advaitic* insight that “reality’s appearance as unreality is notice that its self-identity is special and not static” (Gandhi, 2011, p. 105) to mean that the *Brahman's* expression in the form of the world is not a fall from truth but an active reflection of truth’s vitality. The reflection of *Brahman* in the form of appearance, he suggests, holds no less ontological power than *Brahman* itself – “the real can have no power greater than its power of appearance as unreality, and the power of resolving the most recalcitrant appearance of unreality into itself” (Gandhi, 2011, p. 105). *Brahman* alone is the sustaining reality behind the world’s harmony. *Māyā*, as the reflection of *Brahman*, exists in the world for the not-self (*un-Ātmic*) to encounter through negation

to redeem itself from its illusion. He draws on the traditional *Vedic* principles of *Viveka* – the discrimination between the real and the unreal – as a necessary movement from darkness to light, death to immortality (Gandhi, 2011). As *Ātman-Brahman* is the only reality, he affirms, the experience of the non-self is integral to self-knowledge: “Not-self is necessarily a feature of *Ātman-Brahman's* self-knowledge by way of negation or rejection” (Gandhi, 2011, p. 111). He reiterates that *Māyā* is not merely a veil to be pierced, but a necessary medium through which the self-realises its infinite nature.

This intricate play of appearance and self-recognition leads Ramchandra Gandhi to assert that the *Advaitic* truth of the oneness of reality is not merely an abstract metaphysical concept, but a lived truth that requires the world for its disclosure. He insists that *Māyā* perfectly reflects *Brahman's* self; it cannot remain unencounterable as a formal impossibility (Gandhi, 2011). As he writes, “The unfurling of *Samśāra*, ambiguous neither-real-nor-unreal *Māyā*, is constitutive of the ‘self-knowledge of *Ātman-Brahman* which requires the thinking, by way of denial, of the thought “I am not *un-Ātman*” and because this thinking is no finite cogitation but the thought of infinite being, *un-Ātman* acquires the space and time and materiality of *Samśāra* (world), an involution and

evolution which together are yet no more than the thinking by *Ātman-Brahman* of the thought that it is not *Asat, Acit, Nirānanda*" (Gandhi, 2011, p. 112).

If the manifold expressions of reality are manifestations of *Brahman*, and if the *Ātman* is essentially non-different from *Brahman*, then a critical question arises: does the self need to strive towards self-realisation? How will the self be able to identify itself as either an ignorant self or a liberated self? The answer for Ramchandra Gandhi seems to lie in the paradox of human existence. As the true nature of self is non-other than *Ātman-Brahman*, but as long as it remains entangled in ignorance, it must consciously journey towards the truth till its attainment. He insists that self-realisation demands a persistent struggle, a ceaseless movement of understanding, regression, and revival against the illusion of seeing the apparent world as the real. To be true to one's true nature as *Ātman- Brahman*, man must reject complacency in *Samśāric* knowledge and resist being satisfied with surface norms and worldly conventions. Instead, he calls for a more profound transformation: the individual must courageously seek a more profound truth of the self and the world, "the metaphysical and alchemical quest which is religion in its true form, beware of unworthy inhuman living on his part along the path of his *Sampradāya*" (Gandhi, 2011, p. 117).

In this vision, he advocates that religious living is not merely adherence to moral or social codes, but a pursuit of the deeper reality that liberates and unifies. It aims at a freedom not confined to moral acceptability but emerges from realising oneness as the ground of all being. As he claims, for a man to make it possible to transcend his ordinary way of life towards a higher realm of understanding, he ought to diligently practice two forms of sacrifice – "a turning inwards in *Yoga*, sacrificing comfortable, complacent credulous outer understanding and allegiance, and a turning upwards in obedience, sacrificing comfortable allegiance to the power of the world and flesh. The sacrifice of inwardness is a sacrifice of superficial mind, the sacrifice in upwardness is a sacrifice of superficial life, together they promise eternal truth and eternal life, *Śiva* and *Kṛṣṇa, Brahman* and *Rāsañlā*" (Gandhi, 2011, p. 117).

Self-realisation demands a rupture from the empirical surface of reality and a movement toward the ultimate, undivided truth. As Ramchandra Gandhi states, "It is only when the shadow seeks and attains to self-knowledge...begins to acquire a mysterious substantiality of its own" (Gandhi, 2011, p. 70), this journey is not about becoming a new self but about unveiling the self that already is. "Śrī Ramana Maharṣi insisted again and again

that no one had to become a *jnānī*, that all are already and eternally *jnānīs*" (Gandhi, 2011, p. 255). He emphasises that the path towards this transcendence may necessitate devotion, *bhakti*, and participation in rituals and practices directed towards the divine. "Advaita is the doctrine of *abheda* between *jīvātman* and *paramātman*; it is not a doctrine of the impossibility of *jīvātman* praying to *paramātman* so as to discover communion and identity in communication" (Gandhi, 2011, pp. 236-237). When such practices are undertaken not as ends in themselves but as means rightly oriented toward truth, they can guide the seeker towards the spiritual realm – realising the self as *Ātman-Brahman* is not merely a metaphysical abstraction but a lived quest that holds profound relevance for the modern spiritual condition. To liberate the self from bondage, one must transcend empirical knowing and egoic attachment, entering a metaphysical and spiritual domain that reveals the ultimate truth – *Brahman*.

Ramchandra Gandhi holds that the attainment of the unity of the self and the other fundamentally alters how one encounters the other, serving as a metaphysical ground for reimagining human relationships that transcend a dualistic outlook by seeing others not as separate entities, but as expressions of the same sacred reality. Rooted in the *Advaitic*

tradition, this ontological vision underpins Ramchandra Gandhi's ethical sensibility, wherein the boundaries between the self and the other are dissolve in the light of shared being. Building on this metaphysical foundation, the following section highlights his efforts to articulate how such a vision can be embodied in the everyday world, where the oneness of the self and the other is affirmed in thought and lived through ordinary relations.

Discovering the Oneness of the Self and the Other in the Mundane World

Overcoming the Illusion of Otherness: Metaphysical Shift to Transformative Action

Ramchandhi Gandhi delves into the mystical realm, where the self and the other are seen as fundamentally united at a deeper spiritual level. However, he asserts that it should be actualised in everyday encounters with the mundane world. He claims that the spiritual union of the self and the other is not alienated from real-world implications and must be brought into everyday life. It is not an unattainable abstract concept; however, it should be the cradle of our ways of life: realising this union must be reflected in our thoughts, actions, relationships, and the diverse ways we engage with the world. He states, "we cannot think *Advaita* without living *Advaitā*" (Gandhi, 2011, p. 250). Amita Chatterjee notes that Ramchandra Gandhi's

dialogical communication foregrounds human relationships rooted in his *Advaitic* vision, in which speaker and listener share a non-dual awareness that enables mutual attunement and ethical responsiveness (Chatterjee, 2013). “My unconcealed simulation or open pretence in communicative behaviour can be regarded as Niskāma karma, an action done essentially for its own sake” (Gandhi, 2011, p. 253). Here, metaphysical transcendence arises not from withdrawal but through relationality within the world. It offers a renewed metaphysical vision in contemporary Indian philosophy.

Ramchandra Gandhi's notion of the spiritual union between the self and the other transpires in the mystical realm but requires actualisation in the mundane world, raising profound philosophical questions. It seems plausible and practical within the philosophical framework. Yet, it confronts significant challenges in actualising its core principle of non-duality, particularly in recognising others as extensions of the self within contemporary socio-cultural contexts. His philosophy posits that realising the nature of the self is not merely intellectual but experimental; it is not alienated from real-world implications and must be brought into everyday life. He interprets *Advaita* through a deep engagement with *Samsāra* (world), viewing it not as an illusion to escape from, but as

the realm in which non-dual awareness is to be realised and embodied. “*Samsāra* is possibility and opportunity and responsibility, neither realisation nor defeat” (Gandhi, 2011, p. 266). He re-envisions *Samsāra* not as a realm to be renounced, but as a vital field for actualising non-dual awareness, an arena wherein ethical responsibility and spiritual insight unfold in unity.

Ramchandra Gandhi's lived *Advaita* resonates with S. Radhakrishnan's formulation of *Advaita* as a philosophy that bridges metaphysical insight with ethical action. Radhakrishnan, in his seminal work *The Hindu Way of Life*, does not advocate a world-negating interpretation of *Advaita*; instead, he acknowledges the *Upanisadic* insistence on the world's relative reality and its instrumental role in self-realisation. The world, while not absolutely real in the *Advaitic* sense, is not a mere illusion; it serves a purpose in the individual's spiritual evolution. “When the Śvetāśvatara *Upanisad* looks upon the supreme as the great *Māyin*, it suggests that this wonderful creation is his product. The *Upanisads* do not support the view that the supreme calls up appearances which have no existence except in deluded minds.” (Radhakrishnan, 2018, p. 41). In the framework of non-duality, the world is not dismissed but affirmed as the field in which the truth of the self is to be discerned and actualised.

Among several prominent Indian thinkers, Sundar Sarukkai, Makarand Paranjape, Veena R. Veeravalli and Arindam Chakrabarti have been selectively referenced for their engagement with the philosophical significance of Ramchandra Gandhi's lived *Advaita*, offering distinct yet complementary interpretations. Sarukkai interprets Ramchandra Gandhi's work, especially *I Am Thou. Meditations on the Truth of India*, as an effort to recover the self not through abstraction but through a lived engagement with the everyday. He notes that Ramchandra Gandhi's writing exemplifies the tension between articulating the unsayable, bridging the divided, and acknowledging the fundamental impossibility of non-dualism (Sarukkai, 2013). Paranjape emphasises Ramchandra Gandhi's insistence on bringing *Advaita* into the world and the world into *Advaita*. For him, the core of Ramchandra Gandhi's thought lies in his commitment to actualising Advaitic truth amid lived experience. Paranjape further argues that Ramchandra Gandhi's reinterpretation of *Advaita* speaks directly to contemporary India's historical and cultural context, reasserting it as a living truth of the nation (Paranjape, 2013). According to Veeravalli, Ramchandra Gandhi's articulation of *Advaita* is not strictly confined to the classical Vedānta tradition or the textual authority of Indian scriptures. Instead, it embraces the

plurality of everyday existence, aiming to reveal its underlying truth or, at the very least, its potential for truth (Veeravalli, 2013). Chakrabarti's contributions offer a deeply personal yet intellectually rigorous appraisal of Ramchandra Gandhi's legacy in his moving tribute, *The Philosopher's Funeral for the Demise of his Beloved Friend Ramchandra Gandhi*. In this piece, he urges scholars and policymakers to seriously engage with Ramchandra Gandhi's original and carefully reasoned defence of a spiritually grounded, socially regenerative philosophy. For him, Ramchandra Gandhi's version of *Advaita* is not only metaphysically resonant but also ethically compelling – embodied in what he calls a “logically elegant *Advaita*-based *ahimsā*” (Chakrabarti, 2007), a non-violence that arises not from passivity but from the realisation of non-duality. Together, these thinkers foreground Ramchandra Gandhi's *Advaita* as a lived, dialogical, and socially relevant practice rooted in deep philosophical insight while remaining attuned to contemporary life's ethical and political challenges.

Ramchandra Gandhi explicitly challenges the prevalent misconception that *Advaita* demands transcendence through withdrawal from the world. Instead, he argues that transcending duality should not lead to the mistaken belief that appearances are merely illusory and thus to be

disregarded (Gandhi, 2011). He sees contemporary societal crises, marked by communalism, environmental degradation, and moral fragmentation, as symptoms of an ontological disconnection. In his view, such dualisms are not merely intellectual errors but obstacles to the lived realisation of *Advaita* (Gandhi, 2005). Suppose we fail to realise the oneness as the ground for manifesting plurality in the mundane world. In that case, all the manifesting plurality will lead to dissonance: “two cannot play; they can only fight and destroy one another in gross or subtle ways. One alone can in play appear to be two and play the great game and unfold all the drama of recovery of self-knowledge” (Gandhi, 2011, p. 255).

He offers a nuanced account of how *Advaita* can harmonise with activism and compassionate action. A compelling example he provides is the ethical response to encourage a helpless child begging on the street. For him, a genuine *Advaitin* cannot dismiss the suffering child as a mere appearance or illusion (*Māyā*). Instead, he must confront and alleviate the child's suffering as part of his spiritual responsibility. This approach illustrates that overcoming the illusion of otherness involves a shift in metaphysical understanding and the undertaking of concrete, transformative action. He insists that such actions to relieve suffering must continue until the illusion of separateness is

truly overcome. He thereby aligns *Advaita* with a radical ethical imperative to serve marginalised children, not as an act of charity but as recognition of the self in the other, which he believes is the correct approach to addressing humanity and the plight of India's impoverished and starving children (Gandhi, 2011).

By referencing the illustration of a helpless child, Ramchandra Gandhi demonstrates the lived realisation of *Advaita*, in which contemplative insight merges with ethical action. As he poignantly states, “It severely tests my faith in the doctrine of the sole reality of *Ātman-Brahman* by confronting me with a persisting illusion that the very opposite of *Saccidānanda* is real, and does not let me rest until that illusion is overcome through energetic and victorious ameliorative and revolutionary action. Additionally, it saves me from the egoistic pride of believing that I have done anything more than overcome an illusion” (Gandhi, 2011, p. 231). His vision of *Advaita* is a call to realise the non-dual in and through the world, transforming both perception and action in the process. Rambachan adds another critical layer in living *Advaita* by arguing that the realisation of Brahman is incomplete without a corresponding ethical transformation. In the Advaitic worldview, he argues that knowledge of the self must lead to recognition of the self in others,

highlighting that the metaphysics of non-duality necessarily culminates in an ethics of non-othering (Rambachan, 2006). Ramchandra Gandhi echoes this view when he writes that addressing the other as soul is not a metaphor but an ontological and ethical necessity (Gandhi, 2011). This ethical call lies at the heart of lived Advaita: not to transcend the world, but to see it rightly – to perceive the sacred in the neighbour, the stranger, the socially excluded. The true test of *Advaitic* realisation lies not in retreat but in how one responds to alterity, difference, and injustice. His philosophy challenges us to enact spiritual vision as a practice of compassionate perception and responsible engagement, a non-duality not merely known, but embodied.

Ramchandra Gandhi's understanding of lived *Advaita* further deepened his ethical engagement, which argues against the dangers of moral pride and escapism that can arise from misinterpreting *Advaita*. A concern central to his philosophical inquiry. He critiques the tendency to mistake spiritual detachment for an excuse to renounce action, arguing that such avoidance is a subtle form of pride. He likens this to a false renunciation of action, in which individuals shirk their responsibilities under the guise of spiritual purpose. For him, this kind of pride is particularly perilous, as it distorts the fundamental essence of *Advaita*, which must

be anchored in humility. “The danger of moral pride, which is no less reprehensible than the complacency of selfish and false renunciation of action” (Gandhi, 2011, p. 233). Extending the metaphysical notion of oneness, he insists on its actualisation in everyday encounters with suffering, warning that living an *Advaitin* life is never easy. It demands a constant negotiation between the ideal of non-duality and the complex realities of a world defined by difference and division.

Addressing the Other as Soul: Ethical Discourse of *Advaita*

Ramchandra Gandhi's notion of addressing can raise several questions: does seeing the other as soul overlook their bodily form, behavioural traits, or a specific kind of being? Can one genuinely regard others as soul without disregarding their empirical characteristics? He addresses this apparent tension by affirming that the act of addressing the other as a soul does not negate their embodied or behavioural specificity; rather, it involves a deeper mode of recognition that transcends objectification. As he writes, “but in being able to see a certain sort of being as the object of an imagined act of addressing, I cut through the details and characteristics of his being, or animal being, and see him as a soul – am able to think of him as himself, and not merely as a being of a certain sort.” (Gandhi, 2019, p. 57). In this

imagined act of addressing, he articulates an ethical relation in which the other is not merely seen as a category of being. However, he is encountered as a singular presence, capable of being called upon and vocatively identified. His ethical vision, grounded in *Advaita*, reveals that to regard another as a soul is to recognise the sacred within the ordinary, a form of recognition that neither erases nor reduces the other's worldly characteristics but cuts through them to affirm the irreducible personhood that underlies all differentiation, "Communication is either saying everything as in saying *Advaita*, or it is the manifestation of the total surrender of agency and ego which is *bhakti*" (Gandhi, 2011, p. 254).

The conviction of self-identity arises not from an experience of the self but through an imaginative act in which one envisions oneself as a soul, addressed by an imaginary other. (Gandhi, 2019). This act of imaginary addressing sustains a minimally caring attitude, suggesting that a silent, ethical relation structures self-consciousness: "To be self-conscious is to imagine oneself as minimally cared for" (Gandhi, 2019, p. 64). The act of addressing, even when imagined, carries an irreducible ethical dimension. To address someone, or to imagine being addressed, is to care for them at a minimum. "In addressing me, you exhibit the fact that you minimally care for

me, you exhibit minimal concern for me...it has a lower limit. For an act of addressing, if it is to be an act of soliciting, and not merely an act of trying to elicit, a communicative response from an audience, it must be minimally respectful of the would-be audience's freedom..." (Gandhi, 2019, p. 63). He sees even the most basic form of recognition, as in self-consciousness, as embedded with ethical responsibility. It links well with *Advaitic* non-duality, where the self and the other are not separate, and the act of address becomes a bridge between them through minimal care.

Ramchandra Gandhi asserts that the essence of *Advaita* lies in recognising the sacred in every aspect of the world, which requires actively confronting and dismantling any form of injustice or discrimination, as these are denials of the fundamental oneness that *Advaita* posits. The journey towards *Advaitin* self-realisation demands that one transcend ego, self-interest, and deeply entrenched social divisions –status, caste, religion, or class. To truly embody the *Advaitic* truth of oneness, one must integrate it into thought, word, and deed, particularly in the face of everyday inequalities, injustices, and disparities. "I love as myself all that is, even in its grossest camouflage of appearance as not-self. I love truly and not compulsorily or self-deceivingly or limitedly and conceitedly altruistically and reversibly all

others because I see none and nothing as other than myself” (Gandhi, 2011, p. 249). While such realisation is arduous, Ramchandra Gandhi points to exemplars such as Śri Ramana and Śri Aurobindo to show that this oneness can indeed be realised and enacted in life: “Sri Ramana tirelessly points out to us he sees only *Ātman-Brahman*, and all are alike to him self-realised beings” (Gandhi, 2011, p. 121). An instance on Śri Aurobindo perceiving *Ātman-Brahman* everywhere in Alipore jail – “Śri Aurobindo in Alipore jail had the vision of Vasudeva everywhere, the prison walls the arms of Vasudeva, the tree in the prison courtyard Vasudeva reaching down to him, the coarse blankets on which he slept the embracing arms of Vasudeva, Vasudeva also all the others prisoners many of whom were hardened criminals and murderers and rejects of civilisation” (Gandhi, 2011, p. 121).

Ramchandra Gandhi nonetheless acknowledges the formidable challenges of practising *Advaita*, the unified reality across all beings. He admits the difficulty of maintaining a continuous, unwavering recognition of the *Ātman* as the sole. However, he does not deny the possibility of its practice. He emphasises that while it requires transcending the natural human inclinations to differentiate or judge based on negative experiences that seem harmful, ugly or contradictory to the idea of a

unified, ultimate reality, fully actualising *Advaita* demands a persistent spiritual discipline to sustain the vision of unity despite the apparent dualities and harsh realities of everyday life. As he states, “to live *Advaita* is not easy. It requires a ceaseless holding fast to the image, idea, power, and glory of *Ātman*, self-consciousness one in all and as the sole central reality of all, hateful or harmful or hideous appearances to the contrary notwithstanding” (Gandhi, 2011, p. 249). He acknowledges the challenge of living *Advaita* in the face of worldly realities, asserting that its realisation demands intellectual assent and a deep spiritual discipline to transcend the deceptive immediacy of appearances.

Can the Oneness be Realised in the Ordinary? Reflection on the lived Non-Dualism of Ramchandra Gandhi

Ramchandra Gandhi’s lived *Advaita* raises a compelling question: can the realisation of the non-dual self truly occur in the everyday, embodied context of human life? This question invites a critical engagement with his philosophical intervention. He moves beyond treating *Advaita* as a metaphysical abstraction, relocating it into the sphere of concrete ethical and communicative life. For him, the mundane is not an impediment to realisation but the very medium through which the oneness of existence becomes manifest. In this reorientation, he offers an

ethical ground that arises from the lived encounter between the self and the other. He claims that authentic responsibility towards the other should emerge not from the formal adherence to normative codes, but from the immediacy of relational presence. Ethical action, therefore, must be rooted in mutuality and the recognition of the self in the other, rather than in habit, regulation, or institutionalised morality (Gandhi, 2019). He suggests an ethics of action that emerges from an inner realisation of oneness rather than a mere conformity to external moral codes and norms. Such an orientation raises the possibility that if our society is grounded in personal integrity, it may prove more sustainable than relying primarily on man-made moral prescriptions, inviting further reflection on the adequacy of the conventional ethical framework of our present society.

While the conventional moral thought distinguishes intentional actions from mere events, Ramchandra Gandhi challenges the sufficiency of intentionality as the sole basis for moral action. Though necessary, intentionality requires causal explanation, which, for him, is inadequate to capture the depth of ethical life. (Gandhi, 2019). Instead, his *Advaitic* ethics rests on seeing self and other as sacred presences, irreducible to social roles or identities. In his vision, moral actions should flow from a

fundamental respect for others, not merely from the intentional pursuit of moral ends. As P.R. Bhat notes, while Ramchandra Gandhi's philosophy is grounded in moral responsibility, it surpasses conventional ethical formulations by affirming the uniqueness of the other as an unavoidable ethical value (Bhat, 2013). Such a position not only situates the realisation of non-duality in the texture of everyday relationships, but also redefines responsibility as a response grounded in genuine relationality. He offers a distinctive ethical perspective that holds the potential to radically deepen both the moral and spiritual texture of human life. The relevance of his philosophy of oneness is evident in how it permeated his life, as reflected in k. Sridhar's (2007) remembrance. Recalling their first meeting with Ramchandra Gandhi while still students at Mumbai University, Sridhar and his wife observed "an ineluctable touch which was simultaneously abstract and human, a kind of profound simplicity," revealing how his *Advaitic* vision of oneness was embodied in personal encounters as much as in philosophical discourse.

By centring the notion of minimal care within *Advaitic* consciousness, Ramchandra Gandhi makes a profound contribution to ethical discourse, especially in light of human beings' fundamentally self-regarding tendencies. He acknowledged

that “dualistic aesthetic cannot ensure harmony between man and nature, because not all mankind are gifted with saving aesthetic sensibility; and dualistic ethics cannot ensure harmony between man and man because not all mankind are gifted with a capacity for self-sacrifice and an understanding of it” (Gandhi, 2011, p. 214). This limitation undermines the foundations of a sustainable society, as it mistakenly presumes that individuals will naturally make sacrifices for future generations. In contrast, he points to modern acquisitiveness and the erosion of kinship values as factors that diminish the motivation to work towards a collective future (Gandhi, 2011). He instead urges us to cultivate a form of love that becomes possible only through the realisation of oneness between the self and the other. This love transcends the categories of identity and the notions of equality typically employed in worldly associations that ultimately restrain us from discerning the most authentic form of love: “true materiality and substantiality, true hardness and indubitability of existence can only be gained by *mukti*, by an explosion of love of all things and identity with all things” (Gandhi, 2011, p. 31). His outlook constitutes a novel paradigm for understanding and perceiving the world, with the potential to reshape how we look at and relate to reality.

Ramchandra Gandhi firmly believes in incorporating an *Advaitic* consciousness of minimal care to transcend the self-other dichotomy and, at the same time, acknowledges its challenges, yet considers it the only means to foster societal harmony grounded in the intrinsic unity of all beings. He firmly denies understanding *Advaita* as a rarefied set of moral or aesthetic ideals. It requires not mere abstract metaphysical assent but a radical reorientation of thought and action toward the lived experience of oneness. The lived *Advaita* for him offers a viable ontological and ethical framework for addressing injustice, inequality, division, and systemic injustice, not through external compulsion but through a transformation in consciousness and a fundamental reorientation toward the world. As noted by R.C Pradhan, the acceptance and recognition of lived *Advaita* will enable authentic moral communication, rooted in compassion, empathy, and mutual regard, unmediated by institutional or categorical distinctions (Pradhan, 2013). As our present society is structured mainly by social, economic, and gender-based divisions, incorporating Ramchandra Gandhi’s lived *Advaita* will be highly challenging and might even appear abstract or impractical within the contemporary complexities of social and political life. Moreover, embodying non-duality in contemporary society will be more challenging overall, as it demands

continuous ethical vigilance against commodification, exclusion, and domination. But it is due to these challenges that Ramchandra Gandhi's philosophy becomes compelling and urgently relevant to our times, offering a vision of Sacred relationality in a fractured world.

Conclusion

Ramchandra Gandhi's articulation of the *Advaitic* understanding of the self and the other put forward a critical view of the dualistic understanding of the self and the other. For him, sustaining a duality between the self and the other undermines authentic relation and distorts reality. The oneness of the self and the other alone sustains the reality in the world. He firmly stands against the dualistic doctrine that believes in the distinct existence of self and the other; as such, there is an independent existence of the other, and without the existence of others, there can be no relations. He believes that reality is sustained by the ecstatic union of the self and the other in thoughts and practice. The lived reality prevails in the oneness of the self, and the other, the I, becomes one with the encounter, devoid of all human categorisation and limitations. The union of the self and the other, the thinking subject and the independent object thought of the subject, becomes absorbed into one reality. The *Advaitic* strength lies in elevating the notion of self to the highest form of reality

by eliminating the existence of "I" and "others" in constituting reality, an act of truly addressing another by seeing beyond categorisation and differentiation to recognise the person as a soul – "to think of him as himself, and not merely as a being of a certain sort" (Gandhi, 2019, p. 57). According to Boruah's reading of Ramchandra Gandhi, the soul's reality is contingent upon a particular mode of human engagement, specifically, the attitudinally non-attributive way of viewing another person, suggesting that he locates the soul's presence not in metaphysical abstraction but in the depth of human communication (Boruah, 2013).

Ramchandra Gandhi argues that human beings possess the potential to realise the thought of *Ātman-Brahman* and, consequently, to perceive the multiplicity of embodied forms as expressions of an underlying unity. This realisation is made possible by a distinct cognitive orientation that affirms: 'I am no different from Brahman.' Such an orientation enables one to see the world as the manyness of the one, rather than the manyness of the many. In this view, the experience of oneness does not negate diversity. However, it transforms one's perception of it, allowing embodied forms to be envisioned as non-different from *Brahman* and thus as manifestations of the one.

It can be argued that the rich traditions of *Sanātana Dharma* and the critical frameworks of Western philosophy shaped Ramchandra Gandhi's perspective and articulation of the world's reality, particularly in his understanding of the self and the other. Drawing from the *Advaitic* perception of existence, he affirms a vision in which the self and the others are not separate entities but expressions of an underlying unity. His familiarity with Western philosophical discourse further enabled him to critique dualistic assumptions and highlight non-duality's ethical and ontological depth. Upholding a bold articulation of *Advaitic* as the only means to liberate the world from existential fragmentation. While his thought remains deeply rooted in the philosophical and spiritual ethos of *Sanātana Dharma*, it is primarily oriented toward discovering rightful ways of knowing the self and its relation to the world.

He came to believe that spiritual union should not remain merely an abstract or theoretical concept but must be integrated into individuals' lived experiences. Drawing from the Advaita Vedānta tradition, he highlighted the necessity of recognising the oneness of individual thought and everyday interactions. His methods and frameworks of understanding *Advaita* emphasise the imperative of actualising this spiritual union

in tangible, real-world contexts. He asserts and believes in attaining the spiritual union of the self and the other. He firmly believes that this union should guide and inspire everyday actions. In other words, while the spiritual union is beyond ordinary knowledge, it is not irrelevant to daily lives. Instead, he calls for a deeper ethical and spiritual commitment to how men live and interact with others. His philosophies of self and others are integrated towards the telos of humanity.

Ramchandra Gandhi's teleological and epistemological articulation of the self and the other is grounded in a genuine concern for authentic human relations and a commitment to fostering a just attitude towards the world. His philosophy of oneness, rooted in Advaita Vedānta, challenges conventional notions of selfhood and individuality by asserting that the perceived multiplicity of the self is the root cause of modern anxiety and annihilation. He argues that "anxiety and annihilation are distinctive features of modern civilisation. All anxiety is rooted in the false belief that apparent otherness is real otherness." (Gandhi, 1992, p. 45) For him, the dualistic misperception of the self and the other is the cause of alienation, anxiety, ecological insensitivity, and even self-destruction in modern civilisation. His perspective may be intellectually and morally demanding, particularly for those who uphold rigid

distinctions between the self and the other. Nonetheless, it offers a transformative shift in our understanding of ourselves and others. Especially in today's world, marked by individualism, objectification, ideological conformity, and religious absolutism, his philosophy of oneness offers a compelling ethical alternative that challenges dualistic thinking that merely grounds the moral life in rigid norms. Taking into account the increasing divisiveness of contemporary society seems insufficient to sustain a desirable society through moral norms and conduct. Incorporating Ramchandra Gandhi's lived awareness of non-duality, in which self and other, sacred and profane, are not opposed, can add layers to our ethical relation with the other. This shift from rule-based morality to relational consciousness can provide a firmer foundation for ethical action, urging us toward unity, compassion, and the recognition of shared humanity in an increasingly divided world.

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